

Impact of COVID-19 on Price Shocks on Vegetable Prices in Sindh

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Abstract:

The current research investigates **Impact of COVID-19 on Price shocks on Vegetable prices in Sindh by Using CGE Model**. The 2019-20 corona virus pandemic is an ongoing pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019(COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome. The main objective of this research study to investigates the Impact of COVID-19 on Consumer Price Index (CPI) in Pakistan by using CGE-Analysis. Data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. A consumer survey was conducted from various districts i.e. Sukkur, Shikarpur, Khairpur Mirs, Larkana, Jacobabad and Ghotki. Data were analyzed by using computable General equilibrium model and GEMS-7 version is used for analysis the Data. According to results shows that Coronavirus has impacted on CPI from March to November-2020 the prices of food and vegetables increased by 70 percent because of imports has closed no one can in and out. Due to lockdown situation the demand of vegetables is increasing it is also directly proportional to seller cost.. In Ramzan every fruits runs and mostly fruits comes from outside some are comes from abroad and mostly come from out of province in Larkana so that why supply of these things may decrease it will effect on prizes and availability of these fruits we can take this situation as a positive that some fruits such as mangoes are mostly export and March to October-2020 is the season of its. these will not be exported so may be supply of these increase and prizes decrease.

Key Words: COVID-19, Price shocks, Vegetable, Sindh

INTRODUCTION

The 2019-20 corona virus pandemic is an ongoing pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019(COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome . the outbreak was identify Wuhan, china, in December 2019. The world health organization declared the outbreak to a public health emergency of international on 30 January 2020. As of 19 April 2020 more than 2.32 million cases of COVID-19 have been reported in 185 countries and more than 160000 deaths more than 595000 people recovered. In Sindh first case enter 26feb 2020.

18 February 2020 fruits, vegetables exports hit by coronavirus fruits and vegetables exports are facing problems due to shortage of reefer containers following reduction in the volume of imports china. All Pakistan fruits and vegetables exporters, Importers and merchants association patron-in-chief Waheed Ahmed said it peak export season for kinnow , potato and onion . 100 reefer containers pe day consisting kinnow , potato and onion are being export from Pakistan. Retailers have pushed up prizes of specific food items include sugar and vegetables prices because of mini budget .

Previous prices	Now prices
onion Rs.25 per kg potato Rs.20 per kg tomato Rs. 20-25 per kg ladyfinger Rs. 80perkg cauliflower Rs 50-60perkg peas Rs 40-50 per kg	onion Rs. 30 per kg potato Rs.30 per kg tomato Rs.20-30perkg ladyfinger Rs.120perkg cauliflower Rs 60-80perkg peas Rs.70-80

Literatures reviews

PAKISTAN . The data released shows that higher food prices, particularly of wheat and flour, pulses, sugar, and edible oil, have been the largest driver of overall inflation in January. **Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS) reported on 1feb 2020**

- The UN' Food and Agriculture Organization has warned that protectionist measures by national governments during the coronavirus crisis could provoke food shortages around the world. A shortage of field workers brought on by the virus crisis and a move towards protectionism – tariffs and export bans – mean problems could quickly appear in the coming weeks, the UN's food body explained. Earlier, global agencies have also warned that if authorities fail to manage the continuing coronavirus outbreak properly, world could risk facing a food shortage.
- As per National Food Security & Research Pakistan, there is sufficient stock of wheat/flour in the country and government is going to procure heavily in this season. Whereas the national nutrition survey 2018 showed that 36.9 percent of the population faces food insecurity and food insecurity, definitely leads to an adverse impact on health and nutrition in various ways. .
- Coronavirus will affect agriculture production march 22 2020 new the recent years, global epidemics like SARS, MERS created a negative impact on food security specially for the vulnerable communities. Now that the world population – from developing-to-developed nations – is facing the deadly pandemic called COVID 19.
- A pandemic crisis could quickly put a strain on the food supply chains a complex web to interaction farmers agriculture inputs processing plants retailer's and more . Mexico Cullen the chief economists foe the united nations food agriculture organization.

Research questions:

Q1.Do you think prices for vegetables have increased or decrease du to pandemic?

Q2. Do you think banning the goods transportation has can increase prizes?

Q3. Do you think that demand for vegetables have increased due to lockdown?

Q4 . If imports are banned so will it affect the vegetables or fruits prizes which is consumed during Ramzan.

Literature Review

Anjle, F.M.Shaikh 2020, vegetables prices during Covid -9 pandemic increases in Larkana and people are more suffer during this pandemic period. As stated by (Prof Dr. Abdul Ghafoor Awan & Farwa Saeed 2014) that training enriched employee performance. Findings show that training is an effective and efficient tool for employee's success.

(Miss Bushra Muzaffar 2014) determine that to build a relationship between employee training and employee performance have to design training procedure for employees in TA. Finding proves that training is an essential variable in influencing employee performance.

(Ahmed Mohamed Mohamud 2014) pointed out that training affects employee performance in public sector organizations. Data were collected from 100 staff of the Machakos branch. Findings show training has a momentous impact on employee performance and benefits both the individual employees and the organization at large. (Ngugi Martha Nyakeo Nyokabi 2014) highlighted that training is an essential role in the enhancement of capability of new as well as existing employees for effective performance. Findings show that the training of employees is a very necessary factor of both the organization and the employees therefore; it improves work performance, motivates employees, and builds confidence in the employees. The employees should accomplish knowledge and skills that will assist them in improving or enhancing their performance. Several strategies are actualizing to strengthen the capacity of employees, whilst organization and job design, staffing, PR, rewards, motivation and training & development. By the whole of, Training & Development is that the extremely momentous aspect necessary to accumulate maximal output from the human resources. it's getting to used to elevate or develop job related performance compulsion of the workers. Let examine the subject intimately. Training & Development inform a group of programs designed to reinforce the workPerformance of the workers and organizational productivity. within the modem system, the particular exertion have taken on an honest range of applications, from training in highly specific job skills to long-term professional development, and are appropriate to all or any or any combination of employees ranging from line workers to the Chief officer. Within the present business scenario where learning organization is that the new buzzword, training & development has emerged as a significant corporate function and is recognized as a profession with distinct theories and methodologies. it is a well accepted undeniable fact that an organization's success by and massive depends on how well the workers are performing in their current role. Job performance of an employee depends on several factors like motivation, commitment, and engagement but several researches have reinstated the actual fact that training & development plays the foremost significant part in improving performance of the wor

Research Methodology

Data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. A consumer survey was conducted from various districts i.e. Sukkur, Shikarpur, Khairpur Mirs, Larkana, Jacobabad and Ghotki. Data were analyzed by using computable General equilibrium model and GEMS-7 version is used for analysis the Data.

Results and discussions

Research analysis

Descriptive statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Sno	24	23	1	24	12.50	1.443	7.071
gender	24	1	1	2	1.29	.095	.464
q1	24	2	1	3	1.46	.159	.779
q2	24	1	1	2	1.33	.098	.482
q3	24	2	1	3	1.25	.124	.608
q4	24	0	1	1	1.00	.000	.000
Valid N (listwise)	24						

Statistics

		sno	gender	q1	q2	q3	q4
N	Valid	24	24	24	24	24	24
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		12.50	1.29	1.46	1.33	1.25	1.00
Median		12.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Std. Deviation		7.071	.464	.779	.482	.608	.000
Variance		50.000	.216	.607	.232	.370	.000
Minimum		1	1	1	1	1	1
Maximum		24	2	3	2	3	1

Conclusion

Results shows that Coronavirus has impacted on vegetables or food prizes because of imports has closed no one can in and out. Due to lockdown situation the demand of vegetables is increasing it is also directly proportional to seller cost.. In Ramzan every fruits runs and mostly fruits comes from outside some are comes from abroad and mostly come from out of province in Larkana so that why supply of these things may decrease it will effect on prizes and availability of these fruits we can take this situation as a positive that some fruits such as mangoes are mostly export and May-June is the season of its. these will not be exported so may be supply of these increase and prizes decrease.

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